

Effect of Seed Orientation on Parameters of the Oilseed *Citrullus Lanatus* (Thunb.) Matsum & Nakai

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Abstract

Almost produce in different growing areas in Côte d'Ivoire, oilseed *Citrullus lanatus* constitutes an important source of income and survival for producers. But its traditional practice declines the production of this cucurbit. Heterogeneity of seeds germination after sowing provoked by an unsuitable seed orientation justifies such level of production. In order to find a sustainable solution, some experiences were undertaken in five blocks to test five orientations of seeds: horizontal orientation with the seed on the flattened face (HF), horizontal orientation with the seed on the side (HS), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo down (VD), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo upwards (VU) and any orientation of the seed (Control). The results of the statistical analysis indicated that the parameters tested had been boosted by seeds orientations. Most of those parameters recorded their best values in a horizontal position with the seed on the flattened face. A suitable position of embryo or seed micropyle and an easier circulation of auxin supported this result. Thus, to improve the production of this plant through uniform germination of seeds, it has been recommended to producers mainly women to sow their seeds in a horizontal position with the seed on the flattened face.

Keywords: *Citrullus lanatus*, seed orientation, food security

1. INTRODUCTION

The oilseed *Citrullus lanatus* (Thunb.) Matsum & Nakai belongs to cucurbitaceae family. This plant constitutes a source of income for several people living in west Afrika countries mainly Togo, Ghana, Benin, and Côte d'Ivoire. In Côte d'Ivoire, this cucurbit is produced in four growing areas (North, Center, Center-west) where the climate and soil conditions are favourable to the development of this plant. (Zoro Bi *et al.*, 2006). The peasants know traditionally that the multiplication of this plant is done by its seeds. Base on this opinion, they always use the seeds from the previous harvest to set up new field of *C. lanatus* (Nerson, 2007). Nevertheless, the production of this cucurbit remains below to the food needs of ivorian population. Indeed, in the *C. lanatus* growing areas producers are regularly confronted with problems of seeds germination after sowing. The field observations indicate the lowest rate of seed germination and seedlings emergence. According to Bowers and Hayden (1972), homogenization and speed germination of seeds as well as speed emergence and the seedlings health are influenced by the seed orientation. Thus, the results from the study of Koffi *et al.* (2015) on the cucurbit *Lagenaria siceraria* showed that it is a horizontal position which is suitable to ensure a better germination and seedlings emergence. At the opposite, the seeds of groundnut sprout better when it was sown with the vertical position (Junsik *et al.*, 2017). With regard to the greatest various answers of seeds, the present study has been undertaken to improve the seeds germination of the oilseed *C. lanatus*. Specifically, it is about to work out the suitable positioning in order to success the first step of the production of this cucurbit. Such a database is not available to the oilseed *C. lanatus*.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site

Field experiences were conducted in 2017 on the experimentation site of University Jean Lorougnon Guede (Latitude: 06°53'58"N, Longitude: 06°26'32"W) located in Daloa (Côte d'Ivoire). There are two rainy seasons separated by a short dry period (July-August) and a long dry season (December-February) at the

experimental site. Annual rainfall varies from 800 to 1400 mm with a long-term mean of 1159.33 mm and an annual mean temperature of 27.48°C (Koffie-Bikpo, 2013).

2.2. Plant material and experimental design

Biological material was constituted of 1500 plants of oilseed *C. lanatus* for both periods of sowings. The seeds of those plants were obtained from the cucurbit germplasm of the University of Nangui Abrogoua (Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire). A medium seed size cultivar (NI119) of the indigenous oilseed *C. lanatus* widely cultivated in Côte d'Ivoire was selected.

The trials have been realized on a surface of 57.6 m² (9 m x 6.40 m). After the manual weeding of plots, five sowing beds have been made. Each bed measured 5.40 m on 1.20 m, and they were separated with 30 cm. The experimental design was formed with five blocks kept apart from each other of 0.3 m. Inside of each block, plots were kept apart from each other 0.3 m. On each plot, the sowings were done according to 20 cm between plants with 3 cm deep. During the sowing five treatments have been applied. The treatment consist to sow the seed of the oilseed *C. lanatus* according to five orientations of seeds: horizontal orientation with the seed on the flattened face (HF), horizontal orientation with the seed on the side (HS), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo down (VD), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo upwards (VU) and any orientation of the seed (Control). The experience was conducted in two periods clearly in the month of December and January. After sowing, plots were weeded to prevent competition for water and nutrients in the soil. An insecticide was also applied in order to avoid the damage of seedlings by insects — the absence of rain during experience required to water the different plots. Any fertilizer was applied during the trials.

2.3. Data collection and statistical analysis

12 parameters were measured from the seeds germination to plants flowering: four viability parameters: Germination duration (GD), Germination rate (GR), and Germination speed (GS) and Seedling with integuments, (SI) four vigor parameters: Emergence duration (ED), Emergence rate (ER), Emergence speed (ES), plants mortality rate (PMR), Seedlings length (SL) and Seedlings weight fresh (SWF) and vegetative and flowering parameters: plants creeping duration (PCD), First flower male emergence duration (FFMED), first flower female emergence duration (FFFED). Those parameters were subjected to statistical analysis. Analysis started by comparison between both experiences periods. In case of significant difference between trial periods, the one which provides the best value of parameters tested is chosen for the rest of the analysis. The data from this period is used to test blocks effect. Two ways could result from this last analysis. First, when block effect is not checked, data from whole blocks are put together. Secondly, if the block effect is noticed, it is corrected before continuing analysis. After the two previous tests, a one way analysis of variance is realized to test seed orientation effect on parameters measured. For parameters boosted by this production factor, ANOVA1 is completed by the Least Significant Difference (LSD) multiple range-tests. This test allows identifying one or some parameters which differ significantly to others. All analysis has been done with software program STATISTICA version 7.1.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Effect of sowing periods on viability parameters

Analysis of table 1 shows that the sowing periods affected the three viability parameters tested ($P \leq 0.05$). Thus, seeds from the second sowing periods sprouted early (4.35 ± 0.50) than those of the first period (4.82 ± 1.15). In consequence, seeds sown during the second period recorded the best value speed germination (6.18 ± 0.53) than those of the first period (5.32 ± 0.92). It is also, during the second of the trial that more seeds have sprouted (93.86 ± 4.15).

Table 1: Effect of sowing periods on viability parameters

Parameters	Sowing periods		Statistics	
	P1	P2	F	P
GD	4.82±115 ^b	4.35±0.50 ^a	77.96	0.00
DS	5.32±0.92 ^b	6.18±0.53 ^a	16.37	0.00
GR	85.60±10.58 ^b	93.86±4.15 ^a	13.16	0.00
SI	2.27±0.32 ^a	2.32±0.65 ^a	12.31	0.43

P1: Period1, P2: Period 2, Germination duration (GD), Germination rate (GR) and Germination speed (GS) seedlings with integument (SI), *F*: statistical- F of Fischer and *P*: Probability associated with the test. Mean values within the line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at *P* = 0.05 level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.1.2. Effect of sowing periods on vigor parameters

Statistical analysis realized, indicates that the sowing period affected the four vigor parameters tested ($p \leq 0.05$). The seedlings from the second sowing period take less time to emerge (8.21 ± 0.59) than those of the first period (8.40 ± 1.20). It is also, during this period that seedlings recorded the best value of emergence speed (3.16 ± 0.18). As regards, emergence and plants mortality rate any difference has been noticed between both periods. It is also during the second period the lengthier seedlings have been observed (31.89 ± 9.86) than of first period (18.40 ± 6.40). The heavy seedlings have been obtained during the second period (1.52 ± 0.58) (Table 2).

Table 2: Effect of sowing periods on vigor parameters

Parameters	Sowing periods		Statisticals	
	P1	P2	F	P
EG	8.40±1.20 ^b	8.21±0.59 ^a	11.09	0.00
ES	2.70±0.55 ^b	3.16±0.18 ^a	15.46	0.00
ER	93.87±4.96 ^a	94.83±3.93 ^a	0.58	0.45
PMR	4.73±6.02 ^a	5.36±4.49 ^a	0.17	0.67
SL	18.40±6.40 ^b	31.89±9.86 ^a	817.35	0.00
SWF	1.36±0.34 ^b	1.52±0.58 ^a	12.24	0.00

P1 : Period 1, P2 : Period 2, Emergence duration (ED), Emergence rate (ER), Emergence speed (ES), plants mortality rate (PMR), Seedlings length (SL), *F*: statistical- F of Fischer and *P*: Probability associated with the test. Mean values within the line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at *P* = 0.05 level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.1.3. Effect of sowing periods on vegetative and flower parameters

Vegetative and flowers parameters analysis shows that only the creeping date of plants have been affected by the sowing periods. Thus, the seedlings from the second period crept early (23.21 ± 0.24) than those of the first period (25.32 ± 0.38). As regards emergence dates of flowers male and female, any difference has been observed with the sowing period. (Table 3).

Table 3: Effect of sowing periods on vegetative and flowers parameters

Parameters	Sowing periods		Statisticals	
	P1	P2	F	P
PCD	25.32±0.38 ^b	23.21±0.24 ^a	8.34	0.02
FFMED	37.43 ±1.53 ^a	38.03 ±0.76 ^a	17.54	0.13
FFFED	47.61 ±0.35 ^a	47.75 ±0.75 ^a	14.94	0.65

P1 : Period 1, P2 : Period 2, plants creeping duration (PCD), First flower male emergence duration (FFMED), first flower female emergence duration (FFFED), Mean values within line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at *P* = 0.05 level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.1.4. Effect of the block on viability parameters

The data recorded in table 4 shows that only the germination duration has been affected by the block. The seeds sown in block 1 took less time to sprout (4.50 ± 0.58) than the four others block. As regards, germination speed, germination rate and a number of seedlings with integument, these parameters have been affected the block.

Table 4: Effect of the block on viability parameters

Parameters	Blocks					Statisticals	
	Block 1	Block 2	Block 3	Block 4	Block 5	F	P
EG	8.06 ± 0.95^a	8.36 ± 1.08^{ab}	8.30 ± 1.26^{ab}	8.46 ± 1.21^b	8.81 ± 1.36^c	5.92	0.00
ES	2.84 ± 0.69^a	2.93 ± 0.44^a	2.83 ± 0.63^a	2.80 ± 0.59^a	2.28 ± 0.31^a	1.05	0.40
ER	95.14 ± 5.23^a	96.80 ± 4.45^a	91.89 ± 6.55^a	93.83 ± 4.19^a	91.69 ± 4.06^a	0.94	0.45
PMR	6.66 ± 10.45^a	5.50 ± 4.69^a	4.38 ± 7.23^a	3.04 ± 3.05^a	4.09 ± 3.92^a	0.23	0.91
SL	18.81 ± 7.64^a	15.34 ± 6.11^b	16.94 ± 6.36^b	15.59 ± 6.58^b	17.09 ± 7.07^a	4.62	0.00
SWF	1.48 ± 0.34^a	1.28 ± 0.23^b	1.34 ± 0.24^b	1.33 ± 0.29^b	1.27 ± 0.29^b	9.04	0.00

Germination duration (GD), Germination rate (GR) and Germination speed (GS) seedlings with integument (SI), F: statistical- F of Fischer and Mean values within line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.1.5. Effect of the block on vigor parameters

Analysis of variance shows that three vigor parameters on six have been boosted by the blocks. The seedlings of block 1 emerged earlier (8.06 ± 0.95) than seedlings of block 2 (8.36 ± 1.08), block3 (8.30 ± 1.26), block4 (8.46 ± 1.21) and block5 (8.81 ± 1.36). In addition, the best values of seedlings length (18.81 ± 7.64) and weight (1.48 ± 0.34) have been found in block1. Parameters as emergence speed, emergence rate and rate mortality of seedlings have not been affected by blocks (Table 5).

Table 5: Effect of the block on vigor parameters

Parameters	Blocks					Statisticals	
	Block 1	Block 2	Block 3	Block 4	Block 5	F	P
GD	4.50 ± 0.58^a	4.72 ± 0.75^{ab}	4.92 ± 1.66^b	4.71 ± 0.93^{ab}	5.25 ± 1.35^c	6.78	0.00
DS	5.59 ± 0.72^a	5.32 ± 0.78^a	5.31 ± 1.20^a	5.62 ± 1.13^a	4.75 ± 0.79^a	0.67	0.61
GR	87.33 ± 6.82^a	85.99 ± 10.90^a	84.73 ± 13.32^a	89.33 ± 13.20^a	80.66 ± 10.11^i	0.42	0.78
SI	2.50 ± 5.59^a	0.00 ± 0.00^a	0.00 ± 0.00^a	2.75 ± 6.16^a	0.00 ± 0.00^a	0.75	0.56

Emergence duration (ED). Emergence rate (ER), Emergence speed (ES), plants mortality rate (PMR), Seedlings length (SL), Mean values within line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.1.6. Effect of the block on vegetative and flower parameters

Analysis of data relative to phenology parameters indicates any significative difference between blocks ($p > 0.05$). Whatever blocks considered, plants creeping date, flowers male emergence date and flowers female emergence date have been invariable. (Table 6).

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Table 6: Effect of the block on vegetative and flower parameters

Parameters	Seed orientation					Statisticals	
	HF	HS	VD	VU	Control	F	P
GD	4.49±0.78 ^{ab}	4.37±0.48 ^a	4.70±0.75 ^{bc}	5.71±1.88 ^d	4.84±0.76 ^c	27.78	0.00
DS	6.73±0.76 ^a	6.16±0.24 ^{ab}	5.03±0.77 ^b	4.04±0.68 ^c	5.18±0.39 ^b	7.63	0.00
GR	97.33±6.41 ^a	94.99±4.30 ^a	77.99±8.36 ^b	70.06±6.58 ^t	81.66±7.07 ^t	8.70	0.00
SI	0.00±0.00 ^b	0.00±0.00 ^b	0.00±0.00 ^b	5.25±7.21 ^a	0.00±0.00 ^b	2.49	0.07

Plants creeping duration (PCD), First flower male emergence duration (FFMED), first flower female emergence duration (FFFED), Mean values within line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.1.7. Effect of seed orientation on viability parameters

Analysis of table 7 shows that seeds sown in horizontal position sprout early than those in a vertical position and the control. Thus, the best date of seed germination was recorded in a horizontal position with the seed at the side (4.37±0.48). Seeds sown in a horizontal position at the flattened face recorded the values of the speed germination and rate germination. La position horizontal avec la graine sur la face aplatie donne les meilleures valeurs de la vitesse de germination (6.73±0.76) et du taux de germination. No difference has been found with the seeds sprouted integument. But adhesion of integument was only observed on the seeds sown in a vertical position with the extremity of embryo upwards

Table 7: Effect of seed orientation on viability parameters

Parameters	Blocks					Statisticals	
	Block 1	Block 2	Block 3	Block 4	Block 5	F	P
PCD	24.92±2.05 ^a	24.84±0.43 ^a	25.04±1.43 ^a	24.95±2.30 ^a	25.11±1.45 ^a	7.41	0.53
FFMED	38.57±0.75 ^a	39.03±0.45 ^a	38.89±0.33 ^a	39.34±0.31 ^a	38.92±0.23 ^a	5.63	0.76
FFFED	48.34±0.21 ^a	48.43±0.24 ^a	47.98 ±1.1 ^a	48.12±0.65 ^a	48.20±0.87 ^a	0.43	0.85

Horizontal orientation with the seed on the flattened face (HF), horizontal orientation with the seed on the side (HS), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo down (VD), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo upwards (VU) and any orientation of the seed (Control). Germination duration (GD), Germination rate (GR) and Germination speed (GS) seedlings with integument (SI), Mean values within the line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.1.8. Effect of seed orientation on vigor parameters

Except for plants rate mortality, statistical analysis shows others vigor parameters have been affected by seeds orientation ($P < 0.05$). Seeds are sown in a horizontal position, and those sown in vertical with the extremity of seeds bearing embryo down have emerged early than control and vertical position with the extremity of seeds bearing embryo upwards. The seedlings from the seeds sown in a horizontal position on the flattened face emerge early than those of other orientations (4.85±0.62). Also, more seedlings have been recorded on the plot where seeds were sown in horizontal position comparatively to the other treatments. The lengthiest seedlings have been obtained in a horizontal position with seeds sown on the flattened face (19.33±6.38) and also with those sown in a vertical position with the extremity of seeds bearing embryo down (18.62±8.08). Heavy seedlings were recorded with seeds in a horizontal position on the flattened face (1.45±0.28) and in a vertical position with the extremity of seeds bearing embryo down (1.50±0.29) (Table 8).

Table 8: Effect of seed orientation on vigor parameters

Parameters	Seed orientation					Statistics	
	HF	HS	VD	VU	Control	F	P
EG	7.94±1.27 ^a	8.17±0.84 ^a	8.14±0.81 ^a	9.20±1.53 ^c	8.54±1.00 ^b	21.32	0.00
ES	4.85±0.62 ^a	3.95±0.69 ^{ab}	2.74±0.68 ^b	2.26±0.43 ^b	2.84±0.21 ^b	5.14	0.03
ER	93.02 ±5.25 ^a	95.77 ±6.30 ^a	82.03 ±1.28 ^b	83.02 ±5.88 ^b	74.66 ±5.85 ^b	3.37	0.03
PMR	0.00±0.00 ^a	4.56±3.23 ^a	6.81±7.18 ^a	5.702±1.93 ^a	7.30±11.07 ^a	1.12	0.37
SL	19.33 ±6.38 ^a	15.83 ±6.45 ^b	18.62 ±8.08 ^a	14.59 ±5.78 ^b	15.40 ±6.22 ^b	10.93	0.00
SWF	1.45±0.28 ^a	1.27±0.26 ^b	1.50±0.29 ^a	1.27±0.27 ^b	1.21±0.24 ^b	23.37	0.00

Horizontal orientation with the seed on the flattened face (HF), horizontal orientation with the seed on the side (HS), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo down (VD), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo upwards (VU) and any orientation of the seed (Control). Emergence duration (ED), Emergence rate (ER), Emergence speed (ES), plants mortality rate (PMR), Seedlings length (SL), Mean values within line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.1.9. Effect of seed orientation on vegetative and flower parameters

All the vegetative and flowers parameters in the study have been affected by seeds orientation. Thus, seedlings from seeds sown in a horizontal position with seeds on the flattened face have crept early (23.00±0.00) than those of others seeds orientations. Also, these seedlings recorded the best value male flowers (23.00±0.00) and female flowers (47.00±0.00) emergence dates (Table 9).

Table 9: Effect of seed orientation on vegetative and flower parameters

Parameters	Seed orientation					Statistics	
	HF	HS	VD	VU	Control	F	P
PCD	23.00±0.00 ^a	25.00±0.57 ^c	23.71±0.48 ^b	25.14±0.89 ^c	24.00±0.00 ^b	20.53	0.00
FFMED	37.28±0.48 ^a	40.14±1.06 ^c	38.57±0.53 ^b	39.14±1.95 ^{bc}	39.14±0.69 ^{bc}	6.42	0.00
FFFED	47.00±0.00 ^a	49.85±1.57 ^d	47.28±0.75 ^{ab}	48.57±1.27 ^c	48.14±0.89 ^{bc}	8.24	0.00

Horizontal orientation with the seed on the flattened face (HF), horizontal orientation with the seed on the side (HS), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo down (VD), vertical orientation with the end of the seed bearing the embryo upwards (VU) and any orientation of the seed (Control). Plants creeping duration (PCD), First flower male emergence duration (FFMED), first flower female emergence duration (FFFED), Mean values within line by parameter followed by the same letter(s) were not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ level, on the basis of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test

3.2. Discussion

The present study showed that seeds sown in horizontal position recorded the best values of parameters tested. In general, the future of the different parts of seed or embryo mainly radicle, peg, plumule are under the control of gravity. Thus, radicle or future root has positif geotropism because oriented in the soil for absorption of water, nutrients, and minerals. The peg or future stem has negatif geotropism because opposed to earth center which after leaves emergence will allow realizing photosynthesis. In other words, research the suitable orientation of seeds means simply find a suitable position of the embryo in order to allow its components to really played their rulers. Importance to sow cucurbit seeds in a horizontal position has been signalized by Koffi et al., (2015) working on *Lagenaria Siceraria*. These authors justified their results from

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the positioning of the embryo. Others similar results have been recorded with some plants species. It is the case of *Pterocarpus marsupium* (Mishra *et al.* (2013), *Hardwicki abinata* (Masilamani *et al.*, 1999) and Zewdie and Welka (2015).

Our result could also be explained by an easy penetration of water in the seeds. Signalize before the emergence of radicle and peg the seeds pass through a step of imbibition or rehydration. During this process consist of the penetration of water in dry seeds to set off a physiological process what means that the positioning of the orifice or of the seed micropyle of seed must be oriented in order to make water easier in the seed. For that purpose, Zewdie and Welka (2015) shown importance of seed micropyle orientation of *Milletia ferruginea* and *Dolonix regia* seeds as a condition or indication of suitable seeds orientation du the sowings.

Outside of embryo and seed micropyle orientation, our result could be explained by disturbance absence of physiology process of growth hormone mainly auxin produced and released in the plant growing organ. Indeed, Bennet-clark *et al.* (2001) shown that when seeds are in unsuitable position that leads to an abnormal distribution of auxin in seedlings. According to them, the result of this change is expressed by abnormal growth and morphology of seedlings. In this condition, the lowest value recorded with the seeds sown in vertical position could be led to the reorientation movement of radicle and plumule requiring extra hormone and energy.

The present study also showed that the best values viabilities and vigors had been recorded during the second period of the trial. First period experiment, took place during december characterize by a bad weather harmattan. What indicates absence of rain for plants on the different plots. In other words, crops have been entirely watered with water from the tap. Contrary to this period, in additional water from the tag, plants from the second period have received of rain. Indeed, the first rain of Daloa took place during January. Thus the difference observed between both sowing period could be explained of the abundance of humidity recorded during the trial. Such, explanation has been given by Dje Bi *et al.* (2011) working on the same species. Similar results have been obtained by (Makinde *et al.*, 2009).

Our results also show that the parameters tested have not been affected by the blocks. Uniform growth and development of plants in blocks would be led to the homogeneity of nutrients in the soil. Indeed, the plots used to do the study were previously occupied by three crops mays, okra and soybean. Thus, the harvest waste decomposition would have contributed to the restotation of certains minerals in the soil.

4. CONCLUSION

Increasing crops production is a crucial step to reduce food insecurity in developing countries. In this context, the current study was undertaken to improve oilseed *Citrullus lanatus* production through the innovation of its traditional system. In other words, the purpose of this study was to find a suitable orientation of seeds during the sowing. The results of the statistical analysis indicated that the parameters tested had been boosted by seeds orientations. Most of those parameters recorded their best values in a horizontal position with the seed on the flattened face. A suitable position of embryo or seed micropyle and an easier circulation of auxin supported this result. Thus, to improve the production of this plant through uniform germination of seeds, it has been recommended to producers mainly women to sow their seeds in a horizontal position with the seed on the flattened face.

5. REFERENCES

- i. Bowers SA & Hayden CW (1972). Influence of seed orientation on bean seedling emergence. *Gronomy Journal* 64: 736-738.
- ii. Dje bi IR, Koffi KK, Baudoin J-P & Zoro Bi AI (2011). Effet de la saison de culture et de la densité des plants sur les adventices et la production de la cucurbité oléagineuse *Citrullus lanatus* (Thunberg) Matsum. & Nakai (Cucurbitaceae). *Sciences & Nature* 8 (1): 85 - 93.

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- iii. Junsik A, Song I, Kim D, Lee J, L., Moon S, Myoung S & Kisung K (2017). *Effect of peanut seed orientation on germination, seedling biomass, and morphology in an oak tree sawdust cultivation system. Horticultural science and technology* 35 (4): 402-409.
- iv. Koffi KK, N'goran KB, Kouakou KL, Kouassi KI, Baudoin JP & Zoro Bi IA (2015). *Effects of Seed orientation and sowing depths on Germination, Seedling vigor and yield in Oleaginous type of Bottle gourd, Lagenaria siceraria (Molina Standl). International Research Journal of Biological Sciences* 4 (12): 46-53.
- v. Koffie-Bikpo CY & KRA KS (2013). *La région du Haut-Sassandra dans la distribution des produits vivriers agricoles en Côte d'Ivoire Université Félix Houphouët-Boigny de Cocody / Abidjan / Côte d'Ivoire*
- vi. Makinde AA, Bello NJ, Olasantan FO & Adebisi MA (2009). *Hydrothermal effects on the performance of maize and cucumber intercrop in a tropical wet and dry climate in Nigeria African Journal of Agricultural Research* 4 (3): 225-235.
- vii. Masilamani P, Gurudev S, B., Chinnusamy C & Annadurai K (1999). *Influence of seed orientation and depth of sowing on germination and vigour of Anjan (Hardwickia binata Roxb). ytopieal Adricultural Research and Extension* 2 (1): 76-78.
- viii. Nerson H (2007). *Seed production and germinability of cucurbit crops. Seed Science and Biotechnology* 1 (1): 1-10.
- ix. Zoro Bi IA, Djé Y, Koffi KK, Djé Y, Malice M & Baudoin JP (2006). *Indigenous cucurbits of Côte d'Ivoire: a review of their genetic resources. Sciences et Nature* 3 (1): 1-9.
- x. Zoro Bi IA, Koffi KK & Djé Y (2003). *Caracterisation botanique et agronomique de trois espèces de curcubites consommées en sauce en Afrique de l'ouest: Citrullus sp., Cucumeropsis mannii Naudin et Lagenaria siceraria (Molina) Standl. Biotechnology, Agronomy, Society and Environnement* 7: 189-199